

Single Phase Harmonic Current Detection Method Using Arduino Uno

(Kaedah Pengesanan Arus Harmonik Menggunakan Arduino Uno)

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a low-pass digital filter method to obtain the average value of a direct current (DC) signal. An Arduino Uno microcontroller is employed as a low-pass digital filter to replace an analog low-pass filter. This is due to a complex circuit design of analog low pass filter. Also, digital low-pass filter circuits have more advantages than analog low-pass filter circuits which is, digital filters can be programmed without changing or affecting the filter circuit parameters. Butterworth's digital low-pass filter design is capable of filtering as well as reducing the content of harmonic components from distorted current signals. A harmonic current waveform resulting from a non-linear load is assigned as input to a low-pass digital filter. The Arduino IDE software is used to program a code for the first order digital low-pass filter as well as the Butterworth filter. The output signal performance of the two types low-pass digital filters is compared in term of rise time, settling time, ripples current, steady state errors as well as the percentage rate of total harmonic distortion (THD). The results of the study have shown that the Butterworth digital low-pass filter is the better method because of its ability to filter the harmonic current signal gave the lowest percentage of total harmonic distortion compare to first order digital low-pass filter.

Keywords: Harmonic current; Arduino Uno microcontroller; digital Butterworth low-pass filter; digital first order low-pass filter; Total harmonic distortion

ABSTRAK

Artikel ini mencadangkan kaedah penuras laluan rendah digit bagi memperoleh nilai purata isyarat arus terus (AT). Kaedah penuras laluan rendah digit yang digunakan adalah berasaskan pengawal mikro Arduino Uno bagi mengganti penuras laluan rendah analog. Hal ini disebabkan oleh penuras laluan rendah analog mempunyai rekabentuk litar yang kompleks. Selain itu, litar penuras laluan rendah digit mempunyai lebih banyak kelebihan berbanding litar penuras laluan rendah analog seperti ia boleh diprogram tanpa perlu mengubah serta menjejaskan parameternya. Rekabentuk penuras laluan rendah digit Butterworth mampu untuk menuras serta mengurangkan kandungan komponen harmonik daripada isyarat arus yang terherot. Gelombang arus harmonik yang terhasil daripada beban tidak lurus adalah masukan kepada penuras laluan rendah digit. Perisian Arduino IDE telah digunakan untuk memprogram kod pengaturcaraan bagi penuras laluan rendah digit tertib pertama dan juga Butterworth. Prestasi arus keluaran bagi kedua-dua jenis penuras laluan rendah digit telah dibandingkan dari segi masa naik, masa penganapan, riak arus, ralat keadaan mantap serta kadar peratusan jumlah herotan harmonik. Hasil kajian telah menunjukkan bahawa penuras laluan rendah digit Butterworth adalah kaedah yang lebih baik kerana keupayaannya untuk menuras isyarat arus harmonik memiliki kadar peratusan jumlah herotan harmonik (THD) yang lebih rendah berbanding penuras laluan rendah digit tertib pertama.

Kata Kunci: Arus harmonik; Mikropengawal Arduino Uno; Penuras laluan rendah Butterworth digit; Penuras laluan rendah tertib pertama digit; Jumlah herotan harmonik

INTRODUCTION

In the era of globalization with the growing industrial revolution, works in human life have been heavily lean on the use of electrical appliances. The appliances used consists of a wide range of different types of computers and the equipment used in the

offices and industries. The structure of computer consists of combination of electronic components. Equipment that consists of solid-state electronic components are element of non-linear loads, the main cause of harmonic distortion on a power distribution system. To name the places that have highest rate of electrical appliances application is the commercial centers, industrial and residential areas

where the usage of non-linear loads is high. Some example of non-linear loads is oven, air conditioner, television and laser printer that can draw a non-sinusoidal current to the distribution network. This non-sinusoidal current travels through the system impedance and produce voltage drop which reshape the sinusoidal supply voltage. These distorted voltage and current are called harmonics. There are many ways to eliminate the harmonic problems which by using analog passive filter or analog active filter. However, analog filter has several disadvantages that related to complex circuit design and are difficult to maintain and modify because of complex circuit design.

In this paper, analog signal from a single-phase H-bridge diode rectifier with RLC loads which is in current form (load current) is measured by using ACS712 current sensor before connected to a Arduino Uno microcontroller. The analog signal sampled and converted into digital form by using Analog to Digital Converter (ADC) which is built-in inside the Arduino Uno microcontroller. Then, this microcontroller is programmed to function as a digital low-pass filter to filter harmonic current signal. There are two type of filters used in the experimentation, which is a Butterworth digital low-pass filter and a first order digital low-pass filter. After that, the digital output signal from Arduino will converted to analog by using Digital to Analog Converter (DAC) MCP4821.

Figure 1 shows the basic components of harmonic waveforms, and includes several odd harmonics such as 3, 5, 7 and 11 orders, in power system networks. Because of the symmetry of the sinusoidal waveform so even harmonics do not exist. Harmonics are generally taken place when a non-linear elements source exist in the system (Oguz & Sahin 2016). Harmonic waveforms can be expressed using Fourier series theory. Based on the Fourier series method, even and odd components expression can be presented together. The basic form of the Fourier series equation is:

FIGURE 1. Individual harmonic waveforms
Source: (Oguz & Sahin 2016)

$$f(t) = A_0 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(A_n \cos \frac{2\pi n t}{T} + B_n \sin \frac{2\pi n t}{T} \right) \quad (1.0)$$

The equation above is for a waveform with a continuous period in Fourier series theory, where A_0 is the average value of the function of $x(t)$, A_n and B_n are the coefficients. These three coefficients are obtained by the following equations:

$$A_0 = \frac{1}{T} \int_{T/2}^{T/2} f(t) dt \quad (1.1)$$

$$A_n = \frac{2}{T} \int_{T/2}^{T/2} f(t) \cos n\omega t dt \quad (1.2)$$

$$B_n = \frac{2}{T} \int_{T/2}^{T/2} f(t) \sin n\omega t dt \quad (1.3)$$

where,
 n : harmonic order count

Total harmonic distortion (THD) is the ratio of the sum of harmonic component's root-mean-square (rms) value to the base component's rms value and is normally expressed in percentage. The equation for total harmonic distortion of a voltage is expressed as follow:

$$V_{THD} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} V_{n,rms}^2}}{V_{1,rms}} \quad (1.4)$$

where,
 V_{THD} : THD of voltage
 $V_{n,rms}$: rms voltage for each harmonic order count
 $V_{1,rms}$: fundamental harmonic rms voltage

METHODOLOGY

Figure 2 shows the flow chart of harmonic current detection method and filtering process using the microcontroller Arduino Uno. Starting with the harmonic current detection method by connecting the RLC loads with the H-bridge diode rectifier circuit. Harmonic current is detected by current sensor ACS712. And then the detected signal is fed to the Arduino as input for the filtering process. Microcontroller Arduino Uno is implemented to program and design two types of digital low-pass filter which is Butterworth digital low-pass filter and first order digital low-pass filter. After the filtering process, the digital output signal from Arduino will be converted into analog output signal by using digital to analog converter (DAC) MCP4821. The resulting output signal will be displayed on the oscilloscope in order to analyze its performance and response. It is expected that the digital filters able to filter the distorted signal by showcasing a constant signal without ripple (high frequency component). Figure 3 illustrates the basic schematic circuit design for the proposed low-pass filtering approach using the Arduino Uno microcontroller.

FIGURE 2. Flow chart of harmonic current detection and filtering process

FIGURE 3. Basic circuit schematic diagram for digital low-pass filter design

Design of First Order Low-Pass Filter

A low-pass filter is a filter that only emits/allows a signal that is lower than the predetermined cut-off frequency, f_c . In addition, this filter also blocks the frequency signal above the cut-off frequency, f_c . The following equation indicates a transfer function equation for the first order low-pass filter in the frequency domain (Ronald E. Crochiere, Member 1975).

$$H(s) = \frac{V_{out}(s)}{V_{in}(s)} = \frac{\omega_0}{s + \omega_0} \quad (1.5)$$

$$\omega_0 = 2\pi f_c \quad (\text{rad/s}) \quad (1.6)$$

Next, by converting equation (1.6) to time domain using the MATLAB tool, with parameters of sampling time, $T = 2.0 \text{ ms}$, $f_c = 5 \text{ Hz}$, a time discrete output equation is presented as follows:

$$y(n) = 0.9391y(n) + 0.0609u(n) \quad (1.7)$$

Design of Butterworth Low-Pass Filter

The Butterworth low-pass filter (LPF) is used to separate distorted signal into components of the DC and AC (Bianchi & Singh 2003). By applying the frequency domain transfer function, the feature of Butterworth LPF is expressed as:

$$H(s) = \frac{y(s)}{u(s)} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{s}{2\pi f_c}} \quad (1.8)$$

Using bilinear transform,

$$s = \frac{2}{T} \left(\frac{1-z^{-1}}{1+z^{-1}} \right) \quad (1.9)$$

By substituting s value into equation (1.8), can be further expressed as:

$$H(s) = \frac{y(s)}{u(s)} = \frac{1}{1 + \frac{1}{\pi f_c T} \left(\frac{1-z^{-1}}{1+z^{-1}} \right)} = \frac{\pi f_c T (1+z^{-1})}{(\pi f_c T + 1) + (\pi f_c T - 1)z^{-1}} \quad (2.0)$$

Further, equation (2.0) is switched into time discrete expression:

$$Y[k] = -\frac{(\pi f_c T - 1)}{(\pi f_c T + 1)} Y[k - 1] + \frac{(\pi f_c T)}{(\pi f_c T + 1)} (U[k] + U[k - 1]) \quad (2.1)$$

where, $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$

Experiment Design and Procedure

Figure 4 shown the circuit design of single-phase harmonic current detection method using Arduino Uno. The current sensor (ip+) and (ip-) pins are connected in series to the H-bridge diode rectifier circuit. Pin VCC of the current sensor connects to a 5 V pin Arduino Uno, same goes to the GND pin of the current sensor. The output signal pin, V0 of the current sensor is connected to the analog pin A0 Arduino Uno.

FIGURE 4. Arduino Uno microcontroller connection

On the other hand, pins (CS, SDI and SCK) of the digital converter module to MCP4821 are connected to the Arduino Uno digital pins (10, 11 and 13). Meanwhile, pins (VOUTA and LDAC) are connected to positive and negative oscilloscope probe respectively. Table 1 lists down some parameters of nonlinear load used in the experimental work.

Table 1. Parameters for nonlinear load

Parameter	Value
Input voltage (AC), V_s	49 V_{rms}
Frequency, f	50 Hz
Capacitor, C_o	1000 μF
Resistor, R_o	100 Ω
Inductor, L_o	50 mH

Experiment Equipment

Arduino board is composed of an Atmel 8-bit AVR microcontroller with complementary components to facilitate programming and integration into other circuits as shown in Figure 5. A significant feature of Arduino is the standard way of displaying connectors so that the CPU board can be attached to a number of interchangeable add-on modules known as shields. Some shields communicate directly with the Arduino board over different pins, but many shields can be individually addressed via an I2Cserial bus, which allows many shields to be stacked and used in parallel.

The mega AVR series of chips, specifically the ATmega8, ATmega168, ATmega328, ATmega1280, and ATmega2560, have been used by official Arduinos. Arduino compatibles used a number of other processors. Some boards have a 5v linear regulator and a 16 MHz crystal oscillator (or, in some versions, ceramic resonator). Although some prototypes, such as the Lily Pad, run at 8 MHz and dispense with the on-board voltage regulator because of unique constraints on the form factor.

Figure 6 shows an ACS712 (AC/DC) current sensor that will be used to detect harmonic currents resulting from the bridge rectifier circuit. The current detector able to detect current in the form of alternating current (AC) and direct current (DC). In addition, the current limit that can be detected is according to the current detector model. Briefly, this current detector is divided into three models where the level of current that can be detected is different for each model. up to 30A.

AC712 current sensor has 5 pins, input voltage pin (VCC), ground (GND), analog signal output (VIOUT), input current (IP +) and output current (IP-). The input voltage for this current sensor is 5V (DC) This ACS712 current sensor can be used to measure and calculate the amount of current used on the conductor without affecting system performance. Works by detecting the current flowing in the conductor and generating an output signal proportional to the current detected either in the form of analog or digital voltage.

Figure 7 shown, digital to analog converter MCP4821. This is because, all types of Arduino microcontroller modules don't have inbuilt DAC to convert digital signals to analog. The device module MCP4821 was used to convert the filtered digital current signal through a digital low-pass filter to an analog signal and displayed through an oscilloscope. The device module is equipped with 6 pins, input voltage pin (VCC), 2 earthing pins (GND), synchronization clock pin (SCL), serial data pin (SDA) and Ao pin is an analog signal output pin. The input voltage for this device is from 2.7 to 5.5V.

FIGURE 5. Arduino Uno microcontroller Source:(J.Sathya & Dr.K.R.Valluvan 2019)

FIGURE 6. ACS712 current sensor (AC/DC)

FIGURE 7. Digital to analog converter MCP4821

FIGURE 8. Arduino IDE software

Figure 8 refers to the Integrated Development Environment is the official software for Arduino.cc, which is used to edit, compile and upload programmed code into the Arduino Uno microcontroller circuit board. This application is suitable for all types of Arduino modules. This application can be downloaded for free and openly. This application has also been widely used and there are various references on how to use Arduino IDE. This is because this application is easy to learn and suitable for users who are new to the knowledge of programming language C. In addition, this application can also operate in systems such as MAC, Windows, Linux and even Java platform.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Voltage and Current Harmonic Waveform

Figure 9 show an input voltage waveform as well as a harmonic current resulting from a single-phase diode bridge rectifier circuit connected to an RLC

load obtained from an oscilloscope display. In Channel 1, the yellow wave is the harmonic current wave and channel 2 which is the green wave is the input voltage wave.

FIGURE 9. Voltage and current harmonic waveform produce by bridge rectifier with RLC loads

The Output Signal of Digital Low-pass Filter

FIGURE 10, Output signal of First order digital filter

FIGURE 11. Output signal of Butterworth digital low-pass filter

Figure 10 and 11 shows the waveform of the harmonic current as well as the output current of the digital low-pass filter using an oscilloscope display. Channel 3, the blue waveform is the input current harmonic waveform and channel 1, yellow waveform is the output filtered signal. The output signal has been gained by a multiple value of 100 for First order filter and 60 for Butterworth filter to allow the output data from the Arduino Uno to be received by the digital to analog converter MCP4821. This is because the digital to analog converter MCP4821 can only read data from (0-4096). The average value of the output signal for the First Order digital low-pass filter is 2.9095 V and 1.244 V for Butterworth filter. The output signal value unit is in voltage because the Arduino Uno microcontroller can only generate output voltage and to obtain current output, the output voltage must be connected at load such as resistor to obtain output current. Table 2 and 3 shows the performance output signal of digital low-pass filter. Calculation for performance output signal based on raw data obtained from Arduino IDE.

From the result, Butterworth digital low-pass filter produce better result for rise time and settling time compare with digital First Order low-pass filter. In addition, the Butterworth digital low-pass filter also produces a lower output current ripple than the First Order digital low-pass filter. The percentage of steady state errors produced by the Butterworth digital low-pass filter also lower than the first order digital low-pass filter.

Table 2. Output performance of first order digital LPF

Parameter	Value
Rise time (ms)	62.00
Settling time (ms)	85.00
Ripple current (mA)	79.05
Steady state error (%)	11.53

Table 3. Output performance of Butterworth digital LPF

Parameter	Value
Rise time (ms)	44.00
Settling time (ms)	60.00
Ripple current (mA)	52.79
Steady state error (%)	7.41

Total Harmonic Distortion (THD)

Figure 12, 13, 14 shows the order of harmonic for without filter, Butterworth digital low-pass filter and first order digital low-pass filter using the oscilloscope FFT function.

FIGURE12. Harmonic spectra without filter

FIGURE 13. Harmonic spectra with first order digital LPF

FIGURE 14. Harmonic order with Butterworth digital low-pass filter

Figure 15 below shows the graph bar comparison of harmonic order between Butterworth digital low-pass filter, first order digital low-pass filter and without filter. Table 4 shows the comparison of total harmonic distortion (THD).

FIGURE 15. Comparison of dominant harmonic orders for without filter, first order LPF and Butterworth LPF

Table 4. Comparison of total harmonic distortion

Type of filter	THD (%)
Without filter	99.36
Butterworth	27.65
First order	54.36

CONCLUSION

As a conclusion, the design of Butterworth digital low-pass filter and First Order digital low-pass filter based on the Arduino Uno microcontroller has been modeled and programmed using Arduino IDE and MATLAB software. Based on comparison of performance between the two types of filter, results and current output signal characteristics between the two types of low-pass filters has been analyzed. Based on the results, digital low-pass filters are able to reduce the harmonic current content in the source current signal resulting from the use of non-linear loads such as computers, laser printers and so on

Based on the comparisons that have been made, the Butterworth digital low-pass filter performs better result by having the fastest rise time, and settling time and has a low output ripple current compared to the First Order digital low-pass filter. In addition, the percentage value of the total harmonic distortion (THD) of Butterworth digital low-pass filter is also lower than the first order digital low-pass filter.

The design project of microcontroller Arduino Uno as a digital low-pass filter can be continued by improved hardware and better type of filter such as Trapezoid numerical integration as a continuation proposal and improvement of the study for the future. As suggestion, for better performance microcontroller use Raspberry-Pi.

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REFERENCES

- Acha, A. & Madrigal, E. (2011). Power System Harmonic: Computer Modeling and Analysis. Chichester: John Wiley.
- Arduino. 2016. Arduino - Reference. <https://www.arduino.cc/en/Reference/HomePage>.
- Arrillaga, J. 2017. Power quality. Systems, Controls, Embedded Systems, Energy, and Machines (April), 4(1): 4–14.
- Aswal, J. & Pal, Y. 2018. Passive and active filter for harmonic mitigation in a 3-phase, 3-wire system. Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Inventive Systems and Control, ICISC 2018: 668–672.
- Bianchi, N. & Singh, B. 2003. Design and digital implementation of active filter with power balance theory. IEE Proceedings-Electric Power Applications, 150(2): 139–145.
- Chen, Y.C., Shen, H.Y., Chen, H.Y. & Hsu, C.H. 2016. Low cost Arduino DAQ development and implementation on an android app for power frequency measurement. Proceedings - 2016 IEEE International Symposium on Computer, Consumer and Control, IS3C 2016, 99–102.
- Chung, T.M. & Daniyal, H. 2015. Arduino based power meter using instantaneous power calculation method. ARPN Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences, 10(21): 9791–9795.
- Hidayah, N. 2019. Rekabentuk Dan Perbandingan Prestasi Penapis Lulusan Rendah Kamiran Berangka Menggunakan Algoritma Aturan Trapezoid, Aturan Simpson dan Butterworth. National University Of Malaysia Undergraduate thesis.
- Li Zhongshen. 2007. Design and Analysis of Improved Butterworth Low Pass Filter
- Oguz, Y. & Sahin, M. 2016. Analysing of Harmonics Affecting the Energy Quality in Opium Alkaloids Plant's Power System (March 2017).

Ronald E. Crochiere, Member, I.& L.R.R. 1975. Optimum FIR Digital Filter Implementations for Decimation, Interpolation, and Narrow-Band Filtering. IEEE.

Setsuo, S., Yang, Z.-J. & Wad, K. 1991. Identification of continuous systems using digital low-pass filters. International Journal of Systems Science, 22(7): 1159-1176.

T.J. Freeborn, Maundy, B. & Elwakil, A.S. 2010.

Field programmable analogue array implementation of fractional step filters.

Yusof, Y. 2019. Simplified Control Strategy Of Shunt Active Power Filter Based On Nonlinear Load Equivalent Active Impedance Estimation. Faculty of Engineering, University Malaya PhD. thesis.